

Cohort Based Open Leadership Training and Mentoring

Software Sustainability Institute in partnership with OLS (Open Life Science) and the RCM Cooperative

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Introduction

The Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) Fellowship Programme supports individuals to become recognised ambassadors of good computational and software practice. Central to this is a structured programme of training activities, designed to develop the non-technical skills Fellows need to carry out their plans effectively, maximise their impact, and grow as leaders in the research software community.

Sessions are delivered in collaboration with external partners OLS and the RCM Cooperative, alongside SSI Fellows and staff, and cover a broad range of topics including open science principles, project design, community management, inclusive event management, mental health, and public engagement.

The cohort-based learning programme forms one part of a wider offer of Fellowship support, complementing community calls, study groups, mentorship, seedcorn funding for activities and professional development, and participation in SSI events such as the Collaborations Workshop and Research Software Camps.

The proposed curriculum for cohort-based learning describes a structured learning path for SSI Fellows, drawing on two complementary frameworks:

- The Open Seeds Programme delivered by OLS (Open Life Science Limited), which is a 16-week cohort-based mentorship and training programme focused on open science principles and community leadership.
- Sessions delivered by the RCM Cooperative, which provide foundational and applied training in Research Community Management (RCM).

Aims of the training

The curriculum is designed to achieve the following aims:

- Foster a community of research software ambassadors who champion good computational practice across all disciplines.
- Equip Fellows with practical knowledge of open science principles, reproducibility, and collaborative research methods.
- Develop Fellows' capacity to build, lead, and sustain research communities using evidence-based community management practices.
- Provide structured opportunities for Fellows to apply learning directly within their own research contexts through project-based work.
- Connect Fellows to an international network of open science practitioners, mentors, and experts.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of the programme, Fellows will be able to:

- Define and articulate the principles of open science and explain their relevance to their own research domain.
- Apply tools and frameworks for open project design, including version control, open licensing, and community governance.

- Identify and implement strategies for community building, engagement, and management in research contexts.
- Demonstrate skills in collaborative leadership, mentoring, and knowledge sharing.
- Reflect critically on equity, diversity, and inclusion in research and open science communities.
- Communicate effectively about software sustainability and open research practices to diverse audiences.

Programme Structure

The curriculum is delivered as a series of modules during 4 sessions with two major strands:

Strand	Description	Source
Open Science & Project Leadership	Cohort-based training and peer learning, covering open science principles, project design, leadership, and open research tools.	OLS: Open Seeds Programme
Research Community Management	Introductory and applied sessions on research community management activities with an aim of building sustainable research communities.	RCM Cooperative: RCM 101

The individual sessions are:

Tooling for Project Design	
Overview	Fellows explore practical tools and frameworks for designing open, collaborative projects in a transparent and participatory way.
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify ways for newcomers to quickly understand what the project is about, who can be involved, and where the work is headed • Fill the open canvas for your project to think through an open project strategy to develop a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) • Reflect on the roadmap for your project with milestones and start drafting them with description and tasks • After this session, develop documentation and resources for your project and share them with others

Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cohort call: Tooling for Project Design with expert presentations and demonstrations ● Workshop exercise: Completing the Open Canvas and roadmap for your Fellowship project ● Breakout discussion: Reviewing each other's MVPs and project strategies ● Assignment: Draft project roadmap with milestones and tasks
Deliverable	Completed Open Canvas and draft project roadmap
Source	OLS: Open Seeds Programme
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation slides for Tooling for Project Design session, covering Open Canvas and roadmapping techniques for project management ● Public recording for Tooling for Project Design session, covering Open Canvas and roadmapping techniques for project management

Tools for Open Collaboration

Overview	Fellows learn how to structure their projects to welcome contributions from others, select appropriate licences, and create the essential files that underpin open collaborative projects.
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify essential files to add in a collaborative project ● Explain why you need to select a licence for an open project ● Select the best licence for your project ● Write a clean and welcoming README file ● Discuss the purpose and content of a Code of Conduct
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cohort call: Tooling for Open Collaboration with expert talks and walkthroughs ● Skill-up call: GitHub tutorial for beginners ● Hands-on exercise: Setting up a project repository with README, LICENCE, and CONTRIBUTING files ● Peer review: Giving feedback on each other's repository structures
Deliverable	Project repository created with README, licence file, and Code of Conduct draft
Source	OLS: Open Seeds Programme
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tools for Open Collaboration slides, covering different licences types and how to prepare a README for your own project ● Public recording of Tools for Open Collaboration, covering different licences types and how to prepare a README for your own project

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for Open Collaboration slides, covering ways to develop Contribution Guidelines for an open project and how to define and use a Code of Conduct for Open Collaboration • Public recording, covering ways to develop Contribution Guidelines for an open project and how to define and use a Code of Conduct for Open Collaboration
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Open Science Garden

Overview	The Open Science Garden sessions introduce Fellows to a range of open science practice across research domains. The content was chosen with trainers' input and delivered during two sessions with topics confirmed based on speaker availability and identified needs of the community.
Possible Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science Introduction • Open Source Software • Open Data • Open Access Publication • Open Infrastructures • Open Educational Resources • Open Engagement of Social Actors • Open Hardware • Open Evaluation • Openness to Diversity of Knowledge
Activities	<p>For this cohort, we selected the following two topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science Essentials: covering an introduction to Open Science definitions and frameworks, Open Data work and introduction to FAIR Data • Open Infrastructure: featuring talks showcasing the work of EVERSE, Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) and ELIXIR-UK
Learning objectives	<p>Open Science Essentials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define open science and its core principles, and distinguish between its different components (open data, open code, open publications) to identify what is most relevant to their own work • Apply the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and appropriate licensing to evaluate and improve their own research outputs • Reflect critically on the tension between openness and responsible data sharing, articulating the principle of being "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" <p>Open Infrastructure</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define open science infrastructure, describe its layered and interdependent nature, and identify key infrastructures relevant to their discipline or role • Explain the main sustainability and funding challenges facing open infrastructures, including project-based funding risks, single-funder dependency, and shifting national research policy • Recognise how coordinated advocacy and community governance can secure long-term support for open infrastructure, and connect their own work to existing infrastructure communities
Deliverable	<p>Open Science Essentials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developed a shared understanding of open science and its relevance to their roles as SSI Fellows and research community leaders • Identified at least one open science practice they can realistically adopt or improve in their current work • Gained awareness of key tools and repositories (e.g. Zenodo, ORCID, Software Heritage) that support open and FAIR research practices <p>Open Infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gained a broad understanding of the open infrastructure landscape and the organisations working to sustain it, including IOI, ELIXIR, and EVERSE • Discovered concrete tools and resources available to support their research and community work, including InfraFinder, TeSS, Galaxy, and WorkflowHub • Reflected on the fragility of open infrastructure and their own potential role as advocates for its sustainable funding and governance
Source	<p>OLS: Open Seeds Programme</p>
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public recording for Open Science session, covering an introduction to Open Science definitions and frameworks, Open Data work and introduction to FAIR Data • Presentation slides for Open Science session, covering an introduction to Open Science definitions and frameworks, Open Data work and introduction to FAIR Data • Public recording of Open Infrastructure session, including talks showcasing the work of EVERSE, Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) and ELIXIR-UK • Slides from Open infrastructure session, including reflections by Fotis Psomopoulos on the EVERSE project

Research Community Management I

Overview	Delivered by the RCM Cooperative, this session introduces Fellows to Research Community Management as a professionalised discipline. Fellows explore what it means to build and manage a research community, and begin to apply community management frameworks to their own projects.
Delivered by	RCM Cooperative
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Define Research Community Management and distinguish it from adjacent roles• Understand the RCM Skills and Competencies Framework• Apply the Community Maturation Indicator to assess a community's current developmental stage• Identify community management challenges relevant to your own Fellowship project• Recognise the importance of professionalising community management roles in research
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction: What is a Research Community Manager?• Presentation: The RCM role: professionalisation, skills, and contexts• Group activity: Mapping community management challenges in your own project• Workshop exercise: Applying the Community Maturation Indicator in small groups• Discussion: Recognising and crediting community contributions
Deliverable	Personal reflection: one community management challenge in your Fellowship project and a proposed approach to addressing it.
Source	RCM Cooperative: RCM 101

Research Community Management II

Overview	The second Community Management session, also delivered by the RCM Cooperative, builds on the foundations established in Community Management I. Fellows go deeper into topics such as governance, inclusion, and sustaining communities over the long term.
Delivered by	RCM Cooperative

Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply governance frameworks appropriate to open research communities • Identify and address barriers to participation and inclusion in research communities • Develop strategies for recognising and crediting community contributions • Plan for long-term community sustainability beyond the initial project phase • Reflect on lessons learned from Community Management I and apply them to your project
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cohort call: Community Management II on governance, inclusion, and sustainability • Case study analysis: governance models in open science and research communities • Discussion: contributor recognition and credit systems (e.g., CRediT taxonomy, AllContributors) • Workshop: Developing a community sustainability plan for your project
Deliverable	Community governance plan or updated documentation for your Fellowship project.
Source	RCM Cooperative: RCM 101
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slides for RCM 101 Part One and Part Two sessions • Public recording of Research Community Management 101 - Part One, covering the foundations of research community management, including key roles, skills frameworks, and a reflective activity to map your own competencies and those of your community • Public recording of Research Community Management 101 - Part Two, covering community maturation and engagement strategies, from planning participation levels to mapping your community and prioritising next steps for sustainable growth

Open Leadership in Practice

Overview

A panel session celebrating diverse models of open leadership, followed by community clinics run by the RCM Cooperative where Fellows can bring their own challenges. Open leaders from a range of backgrounds share their experiences, challenges, and strategies for leading open science projects and communities. This session in combination with the community clinics encourage Fellows to reflect on their own leadership journeys and what open leadership means in their context.

Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe different models and approaches to open leadership across sectors and disciplines • Reflect on personal leadership style and growth through the programme • Articulate the transferability of open science and open leadership principles beyond academic research • Identify next steps in your own leadership development
Session Format	<p>Panel of open leaders from diverse backgrounds (academia, industry, NGOs, civic tech, and beyond), followed by a facilitated Q&A and reflection discussion. Panellists are selected per cohort based on availability and relevance to the Fellows' project themes.</p>
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panel presentations: Open leaders share personal stories and leadership approaches • Facilitated Q&A with panellists • Small group reflection: What kind of open leader do you want to be? • Assignment: Personal leadership reflection document
Deliverable	<p>Personal leadership reflection shared with mentor.</p>
Source	<p>OLS: Open Seeds Programme</p>
Resources	<p>Given the confidential nature of the conversations, these sessions were not recorded.</p>

Feedback and evaluation

Pre-Programme Survey

Overview	Ahead of the cohort-based learning sessions, a survey was sent to SSI Fellows to gather insights on their training priorities, preferred formats, and suggested topics. 19 Fellows responded, spanning cohorts from 2015 to 2026, with the majority being from the 2026 cohort.
Rankings of Open Science Garden Possible Topics	Fellows were asked to rank ten open science topics in order of importance. Across all responses, the highest priority topics were: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Open Science Infrastructures: often ranked in the top three across cohorts, reflecting a strong need for understanding the tools and systems underpinning open research● Open Data & FAIR Principles: a close second, with particular interest from Fellows across all cohort years● Open Science Introduction: ranked highly especially by newer Fellows, suggesting demand for foundational knowledge● Open Source Software and Openness to Diversity of Knowledge: both featured regularly in the top half of rankings● Topics ranked as lower priority overall included Open Hardware and Open Evaluation, though a small number of Fellows placed these at the top, indicating niche but strong interest in these areas.
Non-Technical Skills and Topics	Fellows also highlighted a range of soft skills and additional topics they would like to see covered in future sessions, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Research community management: including building and sustaining communities of open-source contributors, organising events and hackathons, and avoiding burnout among community managers and members● Leadership and collaboration: particularly open leadership, influencing organisational change, and working with non-academic partners● Funding and grant management: navigating internal and external funding competitions in a fair and transparent way, and supporting research beyond academia● Project management and science communication: including time management and how to communicate research effectively to broader audiences● Knowledge transfer: understanding how to apply skills across different roles and disciplines, especially for researchers moving into new fields

<p>Preferred Learning Formats</p>	<p>Fellows expressed a strong preference for interactive, hands-on learning over passive formats. The most commonly requested approaches were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and guided tutorials: particularly Carpentries-style approaches where participants can apply learning to their own work in real time • Interactive sessions with take-home materials: reducing the need for note-taking while keeping participants actively engaged • Short, focused formats: including 1-hour webinars, bite-size video series, and reading groups with discussion, reflecting the time constraints many Fellows face • In-person or synchronous sessions: several Fellows noted a preference for live interaction over asynchronous content, though recordings were also highlighted as valuable for those with limited availability <p>A number of Fellows explicitly noted they do not learn well from passive, video-led formats such as LinkedIn Learning-style courses, and would prefer formats that allow for peer exchange and practical application.</p>
<p>Other Feedback</p>	<p>Several Fellows offered additional comments, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One Fellow offered to contribute as a teacher, having experience delivering sessions on Git, open science, and coding principles • One Fellow highlighted the importance of sustainable community management, not just building communities, but keeping them engaged long-term • One Fellow noted that the ranking reflected topics they wanted to learn more about, with topics they already knew ranked lower • One Fellow flagged that competing work demands make it difficult to engage fully with SSI activities, pointing to the value of flexible and asynchronous options alongside live sessions • Recordings and a dedicated asynchronous Q&A channel (e.g. on Slack) were suggested as ways to maximise accessibility for Fellows with busy schedules
<p>Course Feedback</p>	
<p>Overall Engagement</p>	<p>Response rates varied across sessions, with the strongest engagement seen in the earlier sessions. All respondents rated sessions as either 'Very useful' or 'Somewhat useful', with no recorded negative ratings, which highlights the strong overall satisfaction with the training.</p>

Tooling for Project Design & Open Science Essentials (Thu 7 May)	<p>This session was generally well received. Participants particularly liked the introduction to the Open Canvas framework and FAIR principles. Their key takeaways included the importance of open data practices and licensing. Breakout room discussions were often highlighted as valuable.</p> <p>Areas for improvement: Some participants felt concepts could be introduced with more context or a definition and one respondent said they would have preferred more pre-session information. This reflects a balance act that is needed to tailor the session to people with a range of backgrounds and level of expertise.</p> <p>One participant noted that the breakout rooms were occasionally quiet, and more time would be appreciated to work on exercises such as the roadmap. This was the first session so we might need to take more time to introduce the participants to each other before the exercises.</p>
Tooling for Open Collaboration & Research Community Management I (Wed 13 May)	<p>This was one of the highest-rated sessions. Fellows particularly valued the way licensing, README files, Codes of Conduct, and contributor guides were taught together as a complete set. The Darmok Translation Exercise was singled out as especially effective. Presenters were praised for their openness to questions.</p> <p>Areas for improvement: The README exercise would benefit from more time to allow participants to create one for their communities, and the Miro-based activity presented accessibility and usability challenges for some participants. In general, participants really appreciated group activities and would have liked more time for that.</p>
Open Science Infrastructure & Research Community Management II (Thu 21 May)	<p>Well received overall, with Fellows appreciating the time to work on their own and the variety of speakers covering a range of topics that complemented each other. An important takeaway for the participants was the impact of AI on open infrastructure in both a negative and a positive sense.</p> <p>Areas for improvement: Some Fellows found it difficult to relate their own community challenges to the exercises. More time for activities and group discussion was again appreciated, and slide decks shared in advance or at the start of sessions would have been helpful.</p>
Open Leadership in Practice & Community Clinics (Thu 11 June)	<p>Highly rated session. Some Fellows were really touched by the personal and honest accounts shared by the speakers, particularly around career progression, failure, and community building. The open clinic format was also praised for creating a safe and supportive space.</p> <p>Areas for improvement: The community clinic session started slowly but eventually gained speed and was well received. The reason was that many participants had not filled in the pre-circulated template. This is something we will remind participants of more strongly in the future.</p>

Cross-Session Themes

Theme	Feedback
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Breakout discussions	These were valued by participants across all sessions.
Time for group activities	Participants often welcomed more time for this as they found them very valuable.
Accessibility	Some issues were raised in relation to Miro tools and breakout chat functionality
Pre-session materials	A few people requested circulation of materials in advance to better prepare for the sessions.
Peer learning	The cohort or peer element of the training, with participants often attending multiple sessions was highly valued, particularly in clinic and leadership sessions

Summary

The cohort-based learning sessions were well received. Participants particularly liked the peer discussion, practical exercises, and reflections from external speakers. The biggest area for improvement across all sessions is time management. Specifically, allowing more time for activities and group discussion. Accessibility of tools and clarity of exercise instructions are also important aspects to address for future iterations.

We are also reflecting on the delivery format. Sessions ran from 9:30 to 14:00 and were delivered over the course of two months. This required a considerable commitment from the participants. However, there was a real benefit to this format since it allowed participants to build on previous sessions, which were still fresh in their minds, and rapidly develop their thinking about their activities and communities.

Reducing the delivery to single sessions would make the sessions more accessible perhaps, but also risks losing momentum or the cohort based feel to the sessions.

On reflection, the way forward would most likely be either two full day sessions, as OLS has done previously, or smaller sessions over a longer time period to allow for reflection and growth, as is more typical of OLS's usual training model. For this programme, we deliberately chose a middle ground, testing a half-day format across four sessions as a new approach for this cohort.